

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR FORMING STUDENTS' SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES THROUGH FOLK SONGS

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ANNOTATION

The article describes the effectiveness of the teaching process, methods and techniques used to teach Uzbek folk songs in music culture classes in the system of continuous education, to determine the characteristics of students, to cultivate students' spiritual and moral feelings, attitudes and beliefs through targeted study of different musical genres. The work to determine the level of formation of students through the teaching of songs in the classroom, how to plan to determine the scope, level, content and opportunities of education that can be given to students through the teaching of children's folk songs, the effectiveness of the process of teaching Bukhara children's folk songs This solution is a unique stage in the practical study,

acquaintance with the content of scientific and methodological sources, questions and answers created in this field, and the development of theoretical ideas. to what extent it is proven in practice.

Key words: children's folk songs, melody, rhythm, method, method, education and upbringing, the effectiveness of the teaching process, spiritual-ethical, music culture lesson.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье описывается эффективность учебного процесса, методы и приемы, используемые для обучения узбекским фольклорным песням на уроках музыкальной культуры в системе непрерывного образования, для определения характеристик учащихся, воспитания у учащихся духовно-нравственных чувств, взглядов и убеждений через целенаправленное изучение различных музыкальных жанров. Работа по определению уровня сформированности учащихся посредством преподавания песен в классе, определение объема, уровня, содержания и возможностей обучения, которые могут быть предоставлены учащимся в процессе обучения детских народных песен, эффективность процесса обучения бухарским детским народным песням Это решение является

уникальным этапом практического изучения, ознакомления с содержанием научных и методических источников, вопросов и ответов, созданных в этой области, и разработки теоретических идей.

Ключевые слова: детские фольклорные песни, мелодия, ритм, метод, обучение и воспитание, эффективность учебного процесса, духовно-этический, урок музыкальной культуры.

In many countries of the world, providing musical education to the younger generation is of national importance and is considered an important means of personality formation. In each country, music education ideologically and politically serves the social system of the people. At every stage of human history, the direction of development has been determined on the basis of the law of methodological unity of socio-economic progress. This law has served as a factor in the development of forms of social consciousness such as science, art, culture, production, and lifestyle, based on the socio-economic views, ideas, and ideals prevailing in society. Thus, throughout historical development, the rich spiritual heritage accumulated in the upbringing and maturation of a well-rounded individual has been reflected in folk pedagogy. Therefore, in preparing future specialists, it is necessary to focus primarily on familiarizing them with this spiritual heritage — the main

educational and moral ideas contained in folk songs - so that they acquire the knowledge, skills, and competencies that will form a foundation for their effective use in future professional activities.

The peoples of Central Asia, in particular the Uzbek people and their cultural and educational development, have evolved over centuries, and the ideas of upbringing have embodied the essence of socio-political processes of different periods. The educational thoughts and ideas created by our people, as well as the rich heritage related to teaching and upbringing, have nurtured thousands of generations in the spirit of universal human values. Therefore, it is not without reason that folk songs, which are the legacy of our ancestors, are considered a unique sphere of folk wisdom and moral guidance.

Folk songs have played an important role for centuries in the moral and educational formation and maturation of our ancestors. In them, the people reflected their spiritual-educational and artistic-aesthetic views, philosophical and ethical concepts, and life-related as well as educational conclusions. An important direction of folk songs is the formation of students' spiritual and moral qualities, and one of their significant features is the preservation of national characteristics. In studying the ancient history, distinctive features, and types of Uzbek folk songs, the work "Devonu Lug'otit Turk" by the great linguist scholar Mahmud Kashgari holds an important place. While traveling for many years and studying the characteristics of Turkic languages, Mahmud Kashgari collected numerous folk proverbs and songs.

It should be noted that the views expressed in folk songs, as well as the ideas of our scholars regarding the organization of the educational process and the formation of students' human virtues and spiritual-moral qualities, their inclination toward national upbringing, music, melodies, and songs, as well as their preparedness, have not lost their value even today. At all stages of human society, raising a well-rounded individual has remained one of the urgent issues. The national songs of our people demonstrate the existence of a very rich spiritual and educational heritage in this regard.

Thus, in educating the younger generation and in forming their future spiritual and moral qualities, the place and role of the songs created, composed, and performed by our people are extremely significant. In our republic, opportunities are being created to shape the content of education and upbringing and the national ideology, taking into account universal values and the foundations of our national culture. In this regard, work is being carried out to educate a well-rounded individual by teaching folklore, folk pedagogy, and the moral and ethical ideas of thinkers, enlighteners, pedagogues, and scholars. "The future begins today," says our wise people. The future life of the younger generation determines the measure of the spiritual and moral process that shapes them as human beings. In this respect, increasing the effectiveness of education and raising it to the level of world standards, enriching it on the basis of advanced experience, and conducting it on the basis of new pedagogical practices are especially important.

On the basis of folk music, oral creativity, traditions, and customs, raising a harmoniously developed generation creates a foundation for them to love their nation more, to feel pride, to study progressive ideas and teachings, and to apply them to the future. In our independent republic, restoring the uniqueness of our national culture, providing artistic and moral education to students in general secondary schools, and fostering their development are among the urgent tasks of today. A spiritually mature nation gains the ability to correctly evaluate its values and further develop them. Thus, the growth of society's spirituality creates conditions for the wide use of values and prepares the ground for their further development. Based on the definition of values, universal values can be described as a form of values connected with ethnic aspects and characteristics that are significant for a nation. Universal values are manifested through a nation's history, way of life, spirituality, and culture. In the educational process, universal values express a socio-historical phenomenon. Spirituality is a

complex of national customs, educational traditions, moral norms, beliefs, and cultural-educational processes.

Folk songs are philosophical and social concepts that arise as a result of the practical assimilation of the environment surrounding a person. In the process of education and upbringing, the development of students' spiritual and moral qualities through folk songs is considered a socio-historical phenomenon. Alisher Navoi, while providing information about folk songs and their types, substantiated that the words *surud*, *ayolgu*, *lahn*, and *turki* conveyed the meaning of a song.

The purpose of educating today's youth in the spirit of independence, along with increasing the effectiveness of education and upbringing, serves to raise the economic, social, and political potential of our society. The achievement of state independence by the Republic of Uzbekistan opened wide opportunities for the national formation and development of education and upbringing. The theory of national education relies on such disciplines as philosophy, literature, ethics, aesthetics, pedagogy, psychology, and music to substantiate its principles. National education reflects the inner connections and relationships that constitute the essence of life. Today, the demand of the time is to educate not merely knowledgeable youth, but creative students distinguished by their talent. During the period of schooling, national education develops various abilities of students. A system of views toward nature and society is formed, and their physical strength is further strengthened, to which great attention is given. Among the well-known Central Asian musicians, scholars noted that as a child grows older, this activity increasingly acquires an independent character. They gradually learn to understand the phenomena and conditions encountered in nature and social life, to perceive them, and to develop attitudes toward the people around them.

The content and organization of national upbringing based on folk songs are reflected in the following tasks:

1. The purposeful orientation of folk songs.
2. The humanistic principles embodied in folk songs.
3. The connection of folk songs with life and labor.
4. The priority of national cultural and universal values in folk songs.
5. Taking into account students' age, grade level, psychological, and physiological characteristics.

One of the important features of musical art is that it expresses a person's emotions and inner experiences in a unique artistic language. It creates conditions that attract students, engage their interest, and give them enjoyment. It plays a significant role in developing feelings related to national upbringing in them. In general secondary schools, the education of universal values in music culture lessons is formed with the help of melodies and songs. Examples of such works can be found in the State Educational Standard (SES) music curriculum, including songs and listening pieces such as "Salom maktab" (music by Sh. Yormatov), "Paxtaoy" (music by F. Nazarov), "O'zbekistonim" (music by Sh. Ramazonov), "Oy Vatanim" (music by E. Shvarts), and "Eh orzular" (music by N. Norxo'jayev). These songs cultivate in students feelings of love for the homeland and respect for national values.

Introducing universal values to students in general education schools is highly important. In primary grades, when studying universal values, it is necessary to effectively use methods such as conversation, storytelling, question-and-answer sessions, and additional literature. Before learning mass songs based on universal values, it is advisable to conduct a short introductory discussion about the artistic and ideological background and the history of the work. It is also appropriate to connect the study of universal values with other subjects, for example with topics covered in literature lessons.

With fourth-grade students, it is necessary to provide basic information about the main characteristics, popular genres, and traditions of folk music art, explaining that they have a long history and are performed in a simple, fluent, and expressive manner. It is also useful to organize question-and-answer activities about the performers of these works, such as singers, vocalists, and folklore groups. National and universal values are considered a source of national pride. Throughout centuries of labor, struggle, and creativity, they have served as an inspiration guiding people toward goodness. Music is often called “wordless philosophy.” A person lives with song and music; it is difficult to imagine the meaning of life and the beauty of the surrounding world without melodies and songs. A song is a need for enjoyment, a cry of the most beautiful and noble dreams and life ideals. In music culture classes, universal values contribute to the development of students’ worldview and musical taste. 1. Universal values inspire students with appreciation for national melodies and songs. They develop students’ musical abilities, sense of rhythm, musical literacy, and aesthetic taste.

2. They cultivate in students a sense of love for national heritage, popular melodies and songs, folk chants, and through them, love for the homeland. 3. Through lullabies, lapars, and terma songs, students’ artistic and creative abilities gradually develop.

Musical melodies are taught on the basis of modes and rhythmic methods. In forming the national foundation of music education, it is appropriate to use Uzbek national musical instruments together with the piano. In particular, playing the doira, singing songs, performing elements of national dance, and engaging in creative activities captivate students and draw them into the enchanting world of music. In this process, students directly perceive the positive traditions of Uzbek folk music culture. At school, students learn musical and aesthetic education through examples of folk music.

Today, in all general education schools, introducing children to folk music is carried out on the basis of the State Educational Standard (SES) music curriculum. In order to develop education in a national spirit, students are introduced to Uzbek folk music starting from the first grade. As examples from the first-grade listening program, melodies and songs such as “Dutor Bayoti,” “Andijon Polka,” “Farg‘onacha,” “Olmacha Anor,” and “Allama Yorim” can be mentioned. Folk music reaches children’s consciousness quickly, gives them enjoyment, and awakens creative feelings, because folk music possesses a unique artistic language.

It reflects the brightest examples of our national musical art. Folk music is performed in the simplest, most concise, fluent, and vivid melodies. That is why even a baby lying in a cradle becomes calm and falls asleep upon hearing a lullaby. In such melodies, the harmony of words and tune is expressed through oral performance, and therefore the musical phrases are interconnected with one another. For centuries, Uzbek melodies and songs have served as a source of inspiration for our people during labor, weddings, ceremonies, and festive celebrations. In music culture classes, starting from the primary grades, it is necessary to use various methods and innovative technologies in order to convey the popular genres of Uzbek folk music to children in a clear, quick, and expressive way. Compared to other forms of art, music is one of the art forms closest to human beings. Our people have possessed a rich musical heritage since ancient times. Our priceless values and eternal legacy include classical musical art that has amazed the world.

In all periods of social development, the content and direction of education have been determined on the basis of harmony with universal values. Educating and raising students who are intellectually mature, morally pure, physically strong, and aware of their national responsibility creates a foundation for the independent and stable development of the country. National upbringing cannot develop separately from universal human values.

In the present period, the task of nurturing an individual's spirituality requires raising the quality of music education in schools to a higher level. Today, the goals and objectives of music education are extremely important. The purpose of music education is to raise the younger generation as culturally developed individuals who are able to inherit and value our musical heritage. For this, it is directly connected with school music lessons to develop each student's musical abilities, increase their love and interest in the art of music, form the necessary range of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in music, and create the required conditions for the musical growth of talented students. The implementation of the aims and objectives of music education, as well as the formation of spiritual and moral qualities, is directly related to music classes at school. According to the concept of music education, the subject of music holds a special place among other school disciplines. In order to raise the quality of music education, it is considered an equal subject within the school curriculum. This, in turn, requires modern students to have a positive attitude toward lessons, and it demands proper organization, management, and active participation in students' musical activities. Music lessons possess their own distinctive characteristics, and every teacher needs to be aware of these features.

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